

Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook for the Belmont Forum

Collaborative Research Action (CRA) Systems of Sustainable Consumption and Production (SSCP)

Project: Circularity³: Conceptualizing, Implementing and Measuring the Circular Economy from the Micro to the Macro level

Version 1.0

Document change log

Version, year, DOI	Editors	Features
Version 1.0, 2024 DOI https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11047951	Data management team	Initial doc

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1 Introduction

This Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook (DDOMP) is used by the Circularity³ team to specify the procedures the team will follow to manage data, software and other digital outputs. This is a working document and references widely the DDOMP of the PARSEC research team, to whom we are very grateful for their transparent and insightful documentation.

Stall, S., Specht, A., Corrêa, P. L. P., David, R., Edmunds, R., Mabile, L., Machicao, J., Miyairi, N., Murayama, Y., O'Brien, M., Wyborn, L., & Vellenich, D. F. (2023). PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891426>

This document describes the activities required during the project duration of Circularity³, as well as the measures necessary to preserve all digital outputs for future use. It is the intention of the Circularity³ team to make our digital outputs as open, discoverable, accessible and well-documented as possible to ensure transparency, reproducibility and encourage the widest possible re-use. These elements are both recommended and required by the **Belmont Forum Open Data Policy and Principles** and the **FAIR Guiding Principles**.

The Belmont Forum Open Data Policy and Principles state that datasets should be:

- Discoverable through catalogs and search engines
- Accessible as open data by default and made available with minimum time delay.
- Understandable in a way that allows researchers—including those outside the discipline of origin—to use them.
- Manageable and protected from loss for future use in sustainable, trustworthy repositories.

The FAIR Guiding Principles state that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable.

The management of datasets and digital object management will cover the whole project duration. Since all participating organizations will collect and generate data, an overarching data management team consisting of one representative from each participating organization was formed. The data management team appointed lead data managers to coordinate the activities of the team. The team began its work at the start of the project to ensure that the necessary data architecture is in place when data collection and generation starts and will support ongoing data curation, provide the necessary and well-accessible infrastructure, ensure quality control throughout the project and the long term preservation of all objects.

The data and digital object management team members are in alphabetical order:

Malte Besler: Data and digital object lead manager from Fraunhofer ISI, Germany (ORCID: [0009-0008-3686-1255](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3686-1255))

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The data managers support their respective team of researchers in the application of the DDOMP and their development of a data management routine for regular uploads and compliance with the DDOMP. The ongoing responsibilities of Circularity³ team members are described in the [work plan](#) and include:

- **Every upload:** Follow the given file structure and the file naming recommendation: case study number_filename_yyyyymmdd
- **Once a month:** Update the tracking sheets for the output generated in Circularity³ and record software and digital objects used in Circularity³ created by other parties.
- **Every three month:** The ORCID profiles of each researcher need to be updated with the most recent peer-reviewed and non-peer reviewed publications. The DDO management team will meet and discuss further developments of the DDOM routine and barriers and drivers for compliance of researchers in Circularity³ with the DDOMP.

The operating procedures in the DDOMP aim to cover the whole life cycle of data and digital objects from acquisition, material development and temporary storage to licensing and long term preservation and deposition. An overview of the DDOMP in Circularity³ is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Data and digital object journey in Circularity³ based on Stall et al. 2023

2 Operational Procedures (OP)

This section includes the operational procedures of the Circularity team for

1. Selecting datasets requiring preservation
2. Protecting digital objects during the life of the project
3. Ensuring quality of digital objects during the life of the project and prior to preservation.
4. Ensuring data security, privacy, and intellectual property restrictions associated with datasets and digital outputs are honored and preserved in derivative products.
5. Support for inclusive collaboration and authorship for data and digital outputs.
6. Giving attribution for data and digital outputs previously created or created by others.
7. Assigning usage licences to data and digital outputs.
8. Preparing supporting documentation (i.e., metadata) for data and digital outputs that supports public access, discovery, and long-term reuse.
9. Selection of a digital object Preservation Repository
10. Managing sensitive or restricted data
11. Determining costs associated with long-term data management.
12. Project backup and close out.

2.1 OP1: Selecting datasets for preservation

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 1.1 Datasets and other digital objects of long-term value are identified, including data type and encoding, 1.2 How the data and other digital objects will be collected, captured, or created.

The Circularity³ project aims at collecting primary as well as secondary data. Where possible existing data is reused and verified. As not all data needed for the work is already existing, especially information provided by stakeholders, primary data is collected. Datasets significant to our research, as well as any processed or derived datasets, are logged in our [Dataset Tracking excel file](#).

Circularity³ uses existing secondary data that includes academic literature, industry publications and reports, trade data, governmental and intergovernmental data. The project team members also self-collect primary data via questionnaires, surveys, interviews, and workshops, that include customer perception, production data, market outlooks, best practices, and qualitative information regarding circularity. Collected data mainly covers the countries of the project partners and stakeholders: Germany, India, Japan, Taiwan, Thailand, Turkey, and other EU countries (apart from Germany). To ensure that our models are as close to reality as possible, we use stakeholder-based data. We have identified country-specific sources to cover the time frames and scale required.

Circularity³ output data will include micro, meso and macro-level information and data regarding circularity and circular economy of the investigated use cases.

Our primary data and digital products planned for preservation include:

- Collected and cleaned results of stakeholder surveys, workshops and interviews.

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- Compiled scenario data and results of prospective Life-Cycle-Assessments (pLCA)
- Compiled data, results, and models for LCA enhanced Material Flow Analysis (MFA)
- Compiled data, results, and models of business modeling
- Compiled data, results, and models of System dynamics (SD) models and Group Model Building (GMB)
- Compiled data, results, and models for environmentally extended input–output analysis (EEIOA), prospective environmentally extended input–output analysis (pEEIOA), and input output analysis (IOA)
- Algorithms developed to prepare data (cleaning scripts) and perform analyses.
- Training and workshop material

Dataset Preservation: If a dataset is used for analysis, it is to be preserved and made available before the end of the project, or if more time is needed, then before the final report is submitted to the Belmont Forum. We track this in the table where all datasets are logged. For any papers written during the Circularity³ project, datasets used to support that research must be preserved and available at the time of publication.

Software Preservation: All software developed will be preserved at each major release. This includes scripts, computational notebooks, workflows, and models (e.g. Python files, Jupyter notebooks, Vensim models, SimaPro models, etc.).

Training and workshop materials: All materials are to be preserved on or near the time of the workshop.

2.2 OP2: Protecting digital objects during the life of the project

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 4.1 Describe security measures for the data and other digital outputs to prevent unauthorized access with specific examples.

Digital objects are valuable materials, assets, or anything that hold worth in a digital context. Examples of these digital objects include electronic files, documents, datasets, multimedia files (audio, video recordings, and so on), software programs, databases, websites, and other digital information. These digital artifacts contain information and metadata for administration, access, and preservation. Preserving digital objects throughout the project's lifecycle is critical to protecting sensitive data and other digital outputs from unwanted access, theft, or alteration. Security measures must be established throughout the data lifecycle to guarantee its security, integrity, and accessibility. In this context, security measures related to the software, tools etc. To be used throughout this project have been established and listed below to protect digital objects against cyber-attacks, data breaches, unintentional deletion, hardware failures, and other dangers that might jeopardize their integrity or confidentiality.

Material development and data storage during the project: MS OneDrive

Microsoft OneDrive is a cloud storage service provided by Microsoft. It allows users to store and access files and offers features such as file sharing, collaboration, and automated backups. It is

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integrated with other Microsoft applications and access links are easy to share across the working team and partners/stakeholders.

Security measures in MS OneDrive:

- For compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union, data and digital objects are stored on European servers of Microsoft (“Microsoft International Cloud”) using a OneDrive instance provided by the Fraunhofer Society. Data processing, storage, and transport between servers or between servers and the client are encrypted. Access to the data by Microsoft and its partners is contractually, organizationally, and technically prohibited and only takes place in support cases with prior approval by the client (“Customer Lockbox”).
- Microsoft provides security measures that can be viewed here: <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/how-onedrive-safeguards-your-data-in-the-cloud-23c6ea94-3608-48d7-8bf0-80e142edd1e1>

Team communications and information dissemination: MS Teams, E-Mail, Zotero

The team communication is organized through an E-mail list with all project partners and MS Teams. Microsoft Teams is a collaboration tool that enables teams to communicate, meet, call, and work in real-time. It supports file sharing, video conferencing, and interaction with other Microsoft Office apps. Zotero is used to help share literature-related information. Zotero is an entirely free and open-source reference management software that allows users to gather, organize, cite, and exchange research sources. It enables researchers, academicians, and students to collect and arrange references from websites, library catalogs, databases, and other sources. Zotero also includes tools for creating citations and bibliographies in a variety of citation formats, as well as collaborative features that allow users to share references and cooperate on research projects.

Security measures for E-mail communication:

- Minimum security protocols are in place. The E-mail list is updated by the project lead to include all project team members.

Security measures for MS Teams:

- Minimum security protocols are in place. The channel is only available to project team members.
- Data security measures for MS Teams by Microsoft can be viewed here: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoftteams/teams-security-guide>

Security measures for Zotero:

- Minimum security protocols are in place. Interested projected team members can access the Zotero project file.
- Data security and privacy measures by Zotero can be viewed here: <https://www.zotero.org/support/privacy>

Software development: GitHub

GitHub is a popular web-based platform for version management that uses Git, a distributed version control system. It hosts software development projects, letting developers collaborate on code, track changes, and manage processes more efficiently. GitHub's features include code repositories, issue tracking, pull requests, project boards, and continuous integration/delivery (CI/CD) pipelines, making it an indispensable tool for software development teams and open-source communities. GitHub allows a team of software developers to work together with version control, collaboration, and easy access. The Circularity³ repository is located at <https://github.com/Circularity3>.

Security measures for GitHub

GitHub is compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union. Until the publication of the software, the used GitHub pages will be kept private. Two factor confirmation is possible. More information on GitHub security can be found here: <https://github.com/security>

Software and dataset preservation: Zenodo

Zenodo is a well-known general repository that has specialized in software preservation through their partnership with GitHub. It is a general-purpose repository that allows researchers to deposit datasets. It provides DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for easy citation. Zenodo offers a platform for the long-term preservation, curation, and publication of research findings, making them available to the worldwide research community. The Circularity³ repository is located at <https://zenodo.org/communities/circularity3>.

Security measures for Zenodo

Digital objects are stored openly available at Zenodo using a CC BY 4.0 license. More information can be found here: <https://about.zenodo.org/privacy-policy/>

Training and workshop materials preservation: Zenodo

Besides software preservation, Zenodo is used to preserve possible training and workshop materials.

Security measures for Zenodo

Digital objects are stored openly available at Zenodo using a CC BY 4.0 license. More information can be found here: <https://about.zenodo.org/privacy-policy/>

2.3 OP3: Ensuring quality of digital objects during the life of the project and prior to preservation

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: none.

The Circularity³ team has identified a set of criteria to ensure that the quality of the datasets generated by the team through aggregation or analysis meets all the quality requirements and are consistent across the country team. This covers primary data collected during this project and data that is compiled from secondary sources.

Processes to ensure quality and consistency are described and documented for the following criteria:

- 1.) Methods for handling missing data

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- 2.) Methods for handling data at different granularities
- 3.) Methods for handling data using different time series.
- 4.) Use of file naming standards specified in the work plan.
- 5.) Completion and accuracy of meta data (see OP 8)
- 6.) Use of standard vocabulary stated in the common glossary found in OneDrive.
- 7.) Adequate capture of changes made to digital objects to maintain transparency.
- 8.) Tracking of those involved to ensure an accurate list of creators / authors with their ORCID's (see OP 6).
- 9.) Correct level of access and control for sensitive or restricted data (see OP 10).
- 10.) Compliance with all elements defined in the DDOMP (see Code of Conduct).

2.4 OP4: Ensuring data security, privacy, and intellectual property restrictions associated with datasets and digital outputs are honored and preserved in derivative products

*Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 7.1 Describe **intellectual property rights** to the data and other digital outputs.*

The intellectual property rights of primary or secondary data collected or used in the project are listed in the [tracking sheets](#) in order to ensure that copyright and intellectual properties is honored and preserved. Therefore, licenses are either included in the tracking sheets or are assigned for data collected in the project.

Furthermore, all Circularity³ members signed a Code of Conduct document highlighting intellectual property. All signed Code of Conduct documents are securely stored and available for further review.

2.5 OP5: Support for inclusive collaboration and authorship for data and digital outputs.

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: None.

- Promote inclusive collaboration: Actively encourage participation from individuals representing diverse backgrounds and expertise to enrich project outcomes with varied perspectives.
- Ensure equal access: Provide equitable access to data, tools, and resources for all team members, fostering an environment where everyone can contribute effectively.
- Emphasize collaborative authorship: Establish transparent processes for authorship attribution following the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) framework, ensuring that all contributors are acknowledged appropriately, regardless of their role within the team.
- Maintain transparency: Define clear guidelines and procedures for collaboration and decision-making, promoting transparency and accountability to build trust among team members.

By implementing these guidelines, Circularity³ members can effectively support collaboration and authorship for data and digital outputs, leading to more inclusive, innovative, and impactful outcomes driven by the collective efforts of the team.

Meanwhile, to ensure transparency and proper recognition of individual contributions, it is hereby declared that all data management processes within this project will adhere to the CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy) framework. This means that each contributor's role in generating, analyzing, and interpreting the data will be documented and attributed according to the standardized CRediT taxonomy. By implementing CRediT, we aim to promote fairness, accountability, and transparency in acknowledging the diverse contributions of team members to the project's data and digital outputs.

2.6 OP6: Giving attribution for data and digital outputs previously created or created by others

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: None.

The data management strategy for the Circularity³ project emphasizes the importance of giving attribution to all data and digital objects utilized in support of the project, whether they were created by team members or by external contributors. This commitment ensures that proper credit is attributed to the creators of these digital objects.

By signing the Code of Conduct, Circularity³ team members acknowledge and agree to comply with this requirement. It is crucial to highlight that adherence to this established code aligns with the ethical principle that research data and software deserve equal attribution alongside peer-reviewed publications. This practice fosters a culture of integrity, transparency, and recognition of intellectual contributions within the project's framework.

All the data previously created or created by others will also be documented and attributed according to the standardized CRediT taxonomy.

2.7 OP7: Assigning usage licenses to data and digital outputs

*Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 7.2 Describe **licensing** of data and other digital outputs.*

Circularity³ digital outputs are designed to maximize openness while maintaining the necessary level of confidentiality. To achieve this balance, Circularity³ team members are expected to adhere to a set of defined steps. These steps are crucial for promoting the efficient reuse of datasets and other digital objects, whether they are newly created or obtained from external sources. By following these guidelines, the Circularity³ team aims to enhance collaboration, data sharing, and overall efficiency in digital asset management.

To determine the terms of use and licensing for Datasets or Digital Objects (DDO), follow a comprehensive approach in the Circularity³ project. By following these steps, team members can systematically determine and document the terms of use and licensing for Datasets or Digital Objects, facilitating responsible and compliant use of the data.

1. Identify the Source and Ownership:
 - Clearly identify the source of the dataset or digital object.
 - Establish ownership and verify if any specific licensing terms are provided by the creator or owner.
2. Review Existing Licenses:
 - Check if the dataset comes with an existing license or terms of use provided by the creator or distributor.

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- Ensure that you understand and comply with any conditions or restrictions mentioned in the license.
- 3. Consider Legal and Regulatory Requirements:
 - Consider any relevant legal or regulatory requirements that may apply to the dataset, especially country or regional laws.
 - Take into account any indigenous sovereignty governance that may impact the use of the data.
- 4. Credit and Attribution (Please refer OP6 for a detailed description):
- 5. Responsibility and Data Handling (Please refer OP6 for a detailed description):
- 6. Sharing and Communication:
 - Determine whether there are any obligations to share insights or findings derived from the dataset.
 - Understand and adhere to any communication or sharing requirements outlined in the licensing terms.
- 7. Track and Document Usage License (Please refer to the [tracking sheets](#)):
 - Keep a detailed record of the usage license for each dataset.
 - Track any changes in licensing terms and update documentation accordingly.
- 8. Consider Derivative Works:
 - If creating derivative works or derived data products, understand how the licensing terms apply to these modifications.
 - Clearly document the sources and modifications made in the metadata.
- 9. Default Licensing for Created Datasets:
 - For datasets or digital objects created by Circularity3, establish default licensing terms. For example, Creative Commons licenses like CC BY 4.0 or CC0 are commonly used.
- 10. Repository Compatibility:
 - Confirm that the chosen repository or platform supports the desired licensing and access controls.
 - Ensure that the digital object is assigned the most open license possible while complying with any legal or regulatory requirements.

In the Circularity³ project, we adhere to a standard licensing framework for **datasets or digital objects other than software**, and our default choice is the Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license. This license, provided by Creative Commons, allows for the open sharing and use of creative works, emphasizing attribution. Under CC BY 4.0, users are free to copy, distribute, display, and perform the work, as well as make derivative works based on it, even commercially, provided they give appropriate credit to the original creator. The license is designed to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing while respecting the rights of the content creator. This reflects the commitment of openness, accessibility, and the responsible use of digital assets in Circularity³. This applies to primary and secondary data, as well as training and workshop materials.

When it comes to **software** licensing, Circularity³.project will use the GNU General Public License version 3 (GNU GPLv3) which is a more appropriate choice as it permits extensive freedom for users to modify

and distribute software, with the exception of distributing closed-source versions and ensures the continued openness of software projects. It is crucial to emphasize that Creative Commons licenses lack explicit provisions regarding source code distribution, making them unsuitable for software applications, particularly if the intention is to maintain openness for others to use.

2.8 OP8: Preparing supporting documentation (i.e., metadata) for data and digital outputs that supports public access, discovery, and long-term reuse

*Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 8 Describe **supporting documentation and metadata** that will be created to make data and digital outputs publicly accessible, discoverable, and reusable.*

The Circularity³ project team will follow the metadata standards of DataCite 4.4 with the following mandatory metadata criteria:

Criteria	Definition	Example
Identifier	Unique string that identifies a resource. E.g. DOI, ISBN	10.5281/zenodo.11047951
Creator	The main researchers involved in producing the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order.	Besler, Malte
Title	A name or title by which a resource is known. May be the title of a dataset or the name of a piece of software	Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook for the Belmont Forum
Publisher	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource.	Circularity ³ ; Fraunhofer ISI, Germany; Chulalongkorn University, Thailand; University of Bayreuth, Germany; Yasar University, Türkiye; National Taiwan University, Chinese-Taipeh; AIST, Japan
Publication year	The year when the data or report was or will be made publicly available	2024
Resource type	A description of the resource. E.g. "Dataset/Census Data"	Datamanagement/DDOMP

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In addition, the following recommended properties will be included in the metadata where possible and applicable:

Criteria	Definitions	Example
Subject	Subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource	Data and digital object management
Contributors	The institution or person responsible for collecting, managing, distributing, or otherwise contributing to the development of the resource.	
Language	The primary language of the resource	English
Alternate identifier	An identifier other than the primary Identifier applied to the resource being registered, e.g. an original local identifier	
Related identifier (identifier of related resources)	Identifiers of related resources. These must be globally unique identifiers.	10.5281/zenodo.11061763
Size	Size (e.g., bytes, pages, inches, etc.) or duration (extent), e.g., hours, minutes, days, etc., of a resource	821 KB
Format	Technical format of the resource	PDF
Version	The version number of the resource	1.0
Rights	Any rights information for this resource. The property may be repeated to record complex rights characteristics.	CC BY 4.0
Description	All additional information that does not fit in any of the other	

	categories. May be used for technical information.	
Funding and reference	Information about financial support (funding) for the resource being registered	Belmont Forum CRA SSCP
Related items (with respective identifier, creator, title, publication year, volume, issue, number, page, publisher, edition, and contributor sub-properties)	Information about a resource related to the one being registered, e.g., a journal or book of which the article or chapter is part	Circularity3 research project

This is in line with the selected online repository (such as Zenodo) and the [FAIR principles](#). Here are examples of criteria controlled by the repository – identifier, publisher, publication date, and recommended citation. The author names (ORCIDs), affiliations (ROR), and the funder/grant ID will be included in all outputs. In order to produce these metadata files the [DataCite Metadata Generator](#) of the University of Munich can be used.

Software

The Circularity³ use [CodeMeta](#) for each software’s metadata. Their online tool can be found [here](#). This is in line with the [FAIR principles](#) and the selected online repository.

Training and workshop materials

Meta data criteria for training and workshop materials will be added in later versions of the document.

Others

If any domain-specific datasets is produced during the project, for which the previously listed meta data scheme is not applicable, a specific metadata scheme is added to the dataset.

2.9 OP9: Selection of a digital object preservation repository

B Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 2.3 Name of the Repository; 5.1 Repository T&C and/or sustainability plan / cost, 5.2 Entity responsible for managing long-term accessibility

The Circularity³ project understands the need to establish an appropriate digital object preservation repository to ensure the long-term accessibility and integrity of its research results. With the goal of increasing the preservation and accessibility of project data and digital assets, the Circularity³ team is rigorously examining possible repositories using many critical criteria. These include the repository’s

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adherence to digital preservation best practices, compliance with the OAIS Reference Model¹, comprehensive data security mechanisms similar to those given by GitHub and Zenodo, support for preservation metadata, and data access and sharing capabilities. The Circularity³ project intends to use a secure and sustainable platform for storing and sharing its research outcomes, fostering collaboration, and facilitating future data reuse and discovery within the realm of circular economy initiatives by choosing a repository that meets these requirements.

Digital object preservation repositories are electronic systems that store, administer, and guarantee the long-term accessibility and validity of digital objects such as research results and instructional materials. Institutional repositories are especially beneficial for storing and preserving institutions' intellectual output, allowing access to research results, data, learning materials, and image collections. Digital preservation is critical because digital content is fragile and continually changing owing to file formats and technologies. Proactive management reduces the likelihood of format obsolescence, media failure, and discoverability difficulties, providing long-term access to critical digital assets.

The repository terms and conditions define the regulations and standards that depositors and users must follow when using the repository. These phrases frequently refer to issues like copyright, licensing, data sharing, access permissions, and the repository's and users' respective roles. For the Circularity³ project, adopting a repository with explicit and extensive terms and conditions can guarantee that the data and digital objects saved are handled in accordance with agreed-upon standards. It clarifies how project participants and external stakeholders can access, exchange, and reuse data while adhering to legal and ethical guidelines. On the other side, a repository's sustainability strategy relates to its long-term viability and capacity to continue operating in the future. Understanding the sustainability strategy is critical for ensuring that the repository remains active and accessible for the foreseeable future, protecting the Circularity³ project's data for future usage and preservation. Furthermore, the expenses of accessing the repository, such as subscription fees, storage fees, and other charges, must be considered. By analyzing the sustainability plan and related expenses, the project may make educated judgments regarding the financial consequences of using the repository while also ensuring budgetary alignment with its long-term preservation objectives. In summary, the choice of the repository was made according to the criteria:

- Interoperability
- Long-Term Preservation
- Accessibility & Openness
- Metadata Standards
- Versioning & Tracking
- Security Measures
- Scalability
- No or minimal long-term costs

¹ The OAIS (Open Archival Information System) Reference Model is a conceptual framework used in digital preservation to define the functions and responsibilities of a digital archive. Developed by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), the OAIS model provides a common language and framework for discussing and planning digital preservation activities.

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In the context of the Circularity³ project, national repository requirements refer to the specific guidelines, standards, and regulations set forth by national authorities or governing bodies regarding data preservation and management, such as the GDPR. These requirements are crucial for ensuring compliance with national policies and frameworks related to data sharing, preservation, and accessibility. Key aspects of national repository requirements for sensitive or restricted data are specified in OP10: Sensitive or Restricted Data of the Circularity³ DDOMP.

The data management team reviews the accordance of the repositories to the respective national standards.

2.10 OP10: Sensitive or Restricted Data

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 6.1 – Describe how sensitive data and other digital outputs are made available beyond the project team, 6.2 – Describe any limitations on the ability to share data and other digital outputs

The Circularity³ project upholds a commitment to not sharing its sensitive data and digital outputs beyond the project team, all while prioritizing security and confidentiality. To achieve this objective, the project employs a meticulously devised process that includes several crucial steps.

- Legal and Regulatory Compliance
- Metadata Standards
- Data Licensing and Usage
- Data Retention Policies
- Data Formats and Standards
- Data Security and Privacy
- Data Sharing and Collaboration
- Funding and Sustainability

The Circularity³ project requires the gathering, analysis, and management of a variety of potentially sensitive data that is vital to its aims. This includes Personally Identifiable Information (PII), such as names, addresses, and contact information, which, if exposed, might jeopardize privacy and lead to identity theft. Financial data, such as budgets, financing sources, and transaction records, is also deemed sensitive because of its secrecy and possible influence on project strategy. Research results and analysis data, which include raw research data, statistical analyses, and reports, are critical to the project's outcomes and publications, thus they must be protected. Furthermore, customer or partner information, health or medical data, geolocation or location data, sensitive environmental data, ethnographic or sociocultural data, and legal or compliance documents are all important aspects of the project, each with its own set of privacy and security concerns. Safeguarding this broad set of sensitive data is critical to maintaining confidentiality, privacy, and ethical integrity throughout the Circularity³ project's lifespan.

The Circularity³ project pursues a systematic approach to ensuring responsible and ethical data processing without stated use conditions. The team examines the data's sensitivity, origin, and potential ramifications, as well as legal and ethical factors. They provide explicit terms of service and access rules, which are distributed to stakeholders and potential users. The project also aims to employ strong data management methods such as encryption, access limits, and frequent monitoring to ensure data integrity and confidentiality.

2.11 OP11: Determining costs associated with long-term data management

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 9 Describe costs or estimated costs associated with long-term data management or an assigned data manager.

Since all participating organizations will collect and generate data, an overarching data management team consisting of one representative from each participating organization was formed. The data management team appoint lead data managers, who will coordinate the activities of the team. The team began its work at the start of the project to ensure that the necessary data architecture is in place when data collection and generation starts and will support ongoing data curation, provide the necessary and well-accessible infrastructure and ensure quality control throughout the project.

Two main cost components are seen for ensuring the long-term accessibility of the data. The data management team will incur personnel costs during the entire project duration. For each team member, we assume 5% of their allocated budget to be sufficient to cover the expenditure of time. The lead data manager will be allocated 10% of her/his budget for data management. In addition, some project results may be suitable for publication in journals that charge a fee for open access publications. The participating organizations have framework contracts with some publishers, but not with all. Therefore, a yearly budget will be allocated for open access fees. Costs associated with the data and digital object management are:

Acquiring External Data Sources: For the Circularity3 project no acquisitions, involving costs, of external data sources are required.

Quality Check Data: Develop and use common (free) methods for mitigating quality challenges.

Prepare Metadata: Develop and use common (free) templates for data and digital objects.

Data Storage and Backup During Project Duration: Ensure data are protected throughout the project. This includes cloud usage and storage costs (e.g. for MS One Drive).

Data Access and Security: All members of the team, from six countries, need access to the project data and digital objects.

Data Preservation: Includes conversion costs for preparing data.

Publishing: Publishing fees for open access publishing.

Data Sharing and Reuse: Costs for copyright clearance or legal advice. Costs for curation of datasets.

2.12 OP12: Project backup and closeout

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: None.

Determine prior to the end of the grant or project the actions needed to backup and preserve important artifacts not included in the preservation steps for digital outputs (e.g. OP2). This includes the project OneDrive, project website, and other working platforms (e.g. GitHub). These platforms are meant to be working areas used by the team to support the research activities and create digital outputs. They are valuable to the team to review prior work as well as to back up the team's efforts while the work is in progress. However, due to their temporary nature and limited citation capability (e.g. no protection against changes and no assignment of metadata), these platforms are not a good option for long-term storage.

Circularity³: Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook

Project GitHub: Through the iterative nature of GitHub, versions of the developed code will be stored on GitHub. All GitHub repositories not saved for long-term storage that way will be stored prior to the end of the grant or project on Zenodo.

Project Website: The project website will not be maintained after the Belmont Forum grant has ended. The project website content (e.g. files etc.) will be included in the long-term storage via Zenodo. The website itself will be archived in the internet archive Wayback Machine.

Project OneDrive: Regular Backups of the OneDrive project folder are managed by Fraunhofer. All relevant documents not already saved for long-term storage in Zenodo will be stored prior to the end of the grant or project on Zenodo.

Project Teams: As no files are sent via Teams, or all files sent via Teams are also stored in OneDrive there is no need to backup teams.

Project Emails: All files sent via email are also stored in OneDrive, therefore there is no need to backup files within emails. The backup of emails is ensured by the local backups of email accounts within each team member's organization. Only official email accounts are used for communication.

3 **Circularity³: Additional DDOMP Digital Objects**

Belmont Forum Rubric Reference: 1.1 - Types of data and other digital outputs of long-term value, 1.3 - How much data are anticipated, 2.1 - Metadata standards or formats for the data and other digital objects, 2.2 - When data and other digital outputs will be made available outside and within the project team, 2.3 - How data and other digital outputs will be made available beyond the project team, 6.2 - Limitations on the ability to share data and other digital outputs, 7.2 - licensing of the data and other digital outputs

This section provides links to all the digital objects created for Circularity³ grouped by type in the different [Tracking Sheets](#) as well as the [team work plan](#) prompting the time intervals for making sure these lists are updated.

This section includes tracking sheet information for:

1. **Scholarly publications:** Scholarly publications written for the purpose of reporting Circularity³ project related research. These are peer reviewed publications as well as pre-prints.
2. **Non-peer-reviewed digital outputs:** Non-peer-reviewed digital output developed by the Circularity³ project that includes the date of identification, name, metadata standard used, available formats, name of repository, date of initial submission. These objects include posters, presentations, training materials, and workshop materials, organized by the event they were presented.
3. **Datasets log:** Working log of datasets reviewed by the Circularity³ project, including description, filename, metadata standard, licensing, available formats, name of repository, citation, and persistent identifier (e.g., DOI). Note: published Circularity³ datasets are included in Non-peer-reviewed digital output above.
4. **Software log:** Log of software reviewed by the Circularity³ project to include description, filename, metadata standard used (CodeMeta), licensing, language, name of repository, citation, persistent identifier (e.g., DOI). Note: published Circularity³ software are included in Non-peer-reviewed digital output above.

The Circularity³ tracking sheets can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11061764>

The Circularity³ work plan routine can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11093077><https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11061764>

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Preferred Citation:

Project website:

<https://www.belmontforum.org/archives/projects/conceptualizing-implementing-and-measuring-the-circular-economy-from-the-micro-to-the-macro-level>

Zenodo Community:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/circularity3>

GitHub:

<https://github.com/Circularity3>